

carried out using the same soil salinized with NaCl to make water soluble content 0.8% (EC 6.1 dS/m). The soil also was washed with deionized water to reduce salt content to 0.2% (EC <2.0 dS/m) to check varietal vigor without salt stress. Experimental procedures were the same as for preliminary screening.

All varieties grew normally on the soil whose soluble salt had been mostly washed out with deionized water, but badly on the soil with added NaCl.

Although rice growth was generally inhibited by salt, marked differences in salt tolerance were observed (Table 2). Local hybrid Liuyou 33 was one of the most salt-tolerant varieties, comparable with well-known salt-tolerant Pokkali. Local conventional variety Mafeizhan and breeding line IR36/Meijiangzao 3//Guichao also showed relatively high salt tolerance. Moderate salt tolerance was found in widely used local hybrids Liuyou 63, Shanyou 2, Shanyou 63, and Shanyougui 34.

The validity of these results must be verified under field conditions. ■

Table 2. Damage index of varieties or lines in response to salinity.

Group	Variety or line	Seed source ^a	Damage index (%) ^b	Remarks
1	Liuyou 33	LH	66.7 a	Relatively salt-tolerant
	Pokkali	IR		
2	Mafeizhan	LC	73.3 a	
	IR36/Meijiangzao 3//Guichao	LL		
	Nona Bokra	IR		
	IR29725-22-3-3-3	IR		
3	Liuyou 63	LH	80.0 ab	Intermediate in salt tolerance
	Suomali/Daqu//Hongyangai	LL		
	CSR4	IR		
4	Shanyou 2	LH	86.7 ab	
	Shanyou 63	LH		
	Shanyougui 34	LH		
	IR50	IR		
	IR19085-107-1	IR		
5	Shanyou 30	LH	93.3 b	Salt-sensitive
	Shanyou 64	LH		
	Liuyou 6	LH		
	Guanghuaqinglan Fo	LH		
	Liuyou 437	LH		
	Shuanggui 36	LC		
	Siguiai 44	LC		
	Hongyangai 402/Shuangmei	LL		
	Azaipu/Meifeizao 2//Guichao 2	LL		
6	Shuangfei 1/Kezhan	LL	100 b	
	IR36	IR		
	IR54	IR		
	IR2307-247-2-2-3	IR		
	Qingyouzhi	LC		
	Hongyangai 4/Xinmei 1	LL (CK)		
	Qingraixuan/Meifeizao 2	LL (CK)		

^a LH = local hybrid variety, LC = local conventional variety, LL = local hybrid line, IR = variety or line from IRRI, CK = sensitive check. ^b Statistical analysis done after arc sin change of percentage data. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different. Duncan's test, P = 0.05.

Integrated germplasm improvement – irrigated

Liaogeng 287, a high-yielding rice variety for north China

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Liaogeng 287 fits farmer demands for a high-yielding cultivar with multiple resistance and wide adaptability. It was developed from Quling//Sejiangke/Songqian and released in 1988.

In a 4-yr demonstration 1986-89 in north China, yields were 9.2-9.7 t/ha (see table). Liaogeng 287 matures in 145-160 d and is adapted to the band between 35° and 41° N latitude, where one crop rice and rice - wheat cropping prevail. It is acceptable to farmers in Hebei, Shandong, Beijing, Tianjin, and Liaoning Provinces, where it has been planted on more than 53,000 ha.

It is semidwarf (95 cm tall), erect and nonlodging with dark green foliage. Panicle length is 19 cm; 1,000-grain weight, 25.5 g; seed set, 82.3%; protein content, 6.7%; amylose content, 21.8%; alkali spreading value, low; gel consistency, 74 mm. ■

Performance of Liaogeng 287 in farmers' fields. North China, 1989.

Location	Liaogeng 287		Designation	Local check		Increase over check (%)
	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)		Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	
Suangqiao, Beijing	8.3	145	Jingdao 1	7.2	145	15.5
Dongyeng, Shandong	11.4	142	Zhongguo 91	9.3	145	22.6
Yangge, Tianjin	9.2	146	Jingdao 1	8.1	144	13.4
Yinkou, Liaoning	10.1	160	Liaogeng 5	8.6	160	17.4
Shenyang, Liaoning	9.4	160	Liaogeng 5	8.2	160	13.6

Integrated germplasm improvement – rainfed lowland

Multiple-resistance Ruchi released in Madhya Pradesh, India

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Most of the traditional or improved varieties that farmers cultivate in Madhya Pradesh have little or no pest resistance. Recent epidemics of gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood Mason and bacterial blight (BB) *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* have threatened yield stability.

Newly released variety Ruchi (IET 10449, R269-12-1-1) has high resistance to GM, BB, and blast (Bl) and is tolerant of drought. It was derived from the cross R1924/RP9-4. It is